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HUNGARY OPEN ACCESS CASE STUDY

PASTEUR4OA PROJECT
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Hungary Open Access Case Study

Summary

Hungarian OA landscape, policies, challenges are reviewed. There are a few mandates, and a few declarations or policy documents which have relevance for Open Access. The role of the Hungarian Scientific Bibliography Database (MTMT) is discussed – as it can be used for monitoring OA mandate compliance. From infrastructural point of view, the OA status is considered fairly good, from the policy side much further efforts are needed, though the mandate of the Academy of Sciences is elaborate and seems to be effective.

For research data the OA situation is dire in the country. For small countries, like Hungary, the significance of EU-level coordination in shaping OA policies is enormous.

The research and scholarly communication system of the country

In the higher education system of Hungary publicly funded universities are dominant, and the relative weight of private universities is small. Hungary has a chain of research institutes belonging to the Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA). MTA is a learned society, it maintains a series of research centres and institutes, furthermore also acts as a research funder. However, the main research funding organization is the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (OTKA). Hungary has one relatively large scholarly publisher, Akadémiai Kiadó, owned by Wolters Kluwer and the MTA. In the area Science / Technology / Medicine researchers largely publish in international journals, while in the Arts / Humanities / Social Sciences the Hungarian language, local publications prevail.

The Hungarian Scientific Bibliography Database (MTMT) is a nation-wide project, operated by the Library and Information Centre of the Academy (MTA KIK). It is expected to be legally mandatory in the future to record all publications resulting from public funding in MTMT – though the coverage is almost complete already.

Current Open Access Policy Landscape

a) Brief history of development of OA policies in the country

The Budapest Open Access Initiative was issued in Budapest, as a product of a meeting convened by the Open Society Institute. Despite its international long-lasting impact and the fact that projects for making specific scholarly literature openly accessible were already operating in the country¹, the immediate local impact of the Initiative was minimal.

OTKA, the main Hungarian funder, signed the Berlin Declaration in 2008 and issued an open access mandate (covering publications and data). MTA has had an open access mandate since 2012, and the Law on Higher Education has required OA for PhD theses since that year. The organisation of Hungarian open access Repositories (HUNOR) has been active since 2008 and the country participates in SCOAP³.

b) National strategies and policies for OA

Presently there is no national open access strategy or policy. The Law on National Higher Education (2011/CCIV), modified to this effect in 2012, requires PhD dissertations to be made open access, to have DOIs, and be listed in MTMT.

¹ One such project we are aware about is the small journal “Information Bulletin on Variable Stars”, which was openly readable on the web since 1994/95, and from 2000 it had an HTML version with enhanced features.

c) Institutional OA policies

The MTA policy is the only explicit one in the country. It is mandatory, both individual researchers and their institutions are responsible for execution, and monitored using the MTMT. The MTA mandate is 'color-neutral': it allows both gold and green open access. It is also repository-neutral: in case of the green open access, although the MTA repository (called REAL) is the default one, established disciplinary repositories could be used (as arXiv or PubMed Central), and in case of MTA-funded research for University researchers, using the repository of the given University is also possible. The MTA mandate does not cover research data. One important feature of the mandate is that not only the individual researchers bear the responsibility for making publications OA, but the OA compliance of research centres, institutions and groups are evaluated as well.

The MTMT is used to monitor open access compliance statistics for individual researchers and institutions (the project was sponsored by SIM4RDM) and to aggregate the distributed full text content. Compliance with the MTA open access mandate can be monitored on different levels, from the individual researcher through the research institutes and centres, up to the aggregated MTA publication output. However, the Open Access status information is not complete in MTMT yet – for the current year about 44% of the publications are open access, and for about 38% accessibility data is not available, while about 18% is not openly accessible.

MTMT has an almost complete coverage of the national scientific output, therefore Universities or other institutions will be able to benefit from the open access monitoring function in the future.

A few Universities have expressed their intentions to promote Open Access – one has signed the Berlin Declaration, another has policy documents which implicitly deal with Open Access. These are not full-fledged OA mandates, though.

d) Funders OA policies

The OTKA mandate is the only funder mandate. It is mandatory, but it is neither monitored nor enforced. The mandate is not an elaborate, specific document – it appears in the grant contract as two simple statements: all publications resulting from the funding should be made Open Access, using either the gold or green routes; and research data should be deposited in an open access repository. At the time when the mandate was issued, there was no possibility to monitor compliance (besides of asking researchers to report the URLs where their publications are openly accessible – but this option was not pursued). Now the MTMT can be used – if the OTKA funding is properly indicated in the database.

e) Infrastructural support for OA

Repositories are now established at almost all large Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). MTMT can function as a national aggregator for open access publications. Deposit is possible through MTMT to various institutional repositories using the SWORD protocol. MTA has an open access fund to cover gold open access Article Processing Charges (APCs), and OTKA earmarks a part of the overhead for funding open access. HUNOR (HUNGarian Open access Repositories) is a national open access support group, and acts as a communication forum for repositories and advocates open access. The MTMT has a task group for assessment and certification of repositories. The development of a national Open Access (aggregated repository) search portal is under way.

f) Hungarian OA in numbers

There are 29 Hungarian journals in the DOAJ; 28 repositories in Registry of Open Access Repositories; 24 repositories in OpenDOAR (Directory of Open Access Repositories); 3 mandates in the Registry of Open Access Mandatory Archiving Policies; 3 EU project participations (OpenAIRE / OpenAIREplus: Univ. of Debrecen; SIM4RDM: National Information Infrastructure Development Institute (NIIF); PASTEUR4OA: MTA KIK).

Challenges and ongoing developments

Developing national open access policies and strategies is a challenge – and it is envisioned PASTEUR4OA will catalyse progress in this regard. Open access mandates and strategies would be needed for the universities (presently only a few universities have some documents dealing with Open Access explicitly or implicitly, but neither of these are clear mandates, nor do they have any perceptible effects). Agreements between publishers and RPOs issuing open access mandates are needed – MTA has reached an agreement with Elsevier only recently. (In Elsevier's case, they require such agreements for allowing mandatory repository deposits. For all major publishers, agreements could enable MTA make bulk APC payments, instead of the authors paying on an article-by article basis.) Open access for research data is uncharted territory, and not even the need for it is recognised widely. There are some positive developments nevertheless: the MTMT is examining the inclusion of “data” type research output besides of traditional publication, and MTA KIK considers setting up a data repository having recently joined DataCite. Most of the Hungarian publishers have no clear open access policies, and in general are worried about the harmful effects they conceive that open access might bring.

The research funding system of Hungary is under re-organization. There are indications that the new system might be beneficial from the point of view of OA. There is on-going legislation process about the registration of publications resulting from public funding, and there are indications that the government might welcome initiatives regarding a national OA mandate. PASTEUR4OA might catalyse this process.

Conclusions

The status of open access is mixed in Hungary – in some areas it is fairly developed, in other areas it is still rudimentary or lacking completely. The MTA mandate is elaborate and seems to be effective. The national PhD mandate seems to bring some effect after a slow start. But not much other result could be listed on the policy side. The infrastructure is fairly developed, there are many repositories working, or under construction. OA for research Data is where the most developments are needed. For relatively small countries, like Hungary, international cooperation is extremely important, and PASTEUR4OA and strong, uniform European standpoint is necessary.

Useful links

- » **MTMT** (presently only in Hungarian) (<http://www.mtmt.hu>)
- » **Hungarian OA Portal / HUNOR** (only in Hungarian) (<http://www.open-access.hu>)
- » **Library and Information Centre, Hungarian Academy of Sciences** (http://konyvtar.mta.hu/index_en.php)
- » **MTA OA policies and Hungarian OA landscape** (slides of a talk, MedOAnet final conference, Athens, 2013) (<http://www.konkoly.hu/staff/holl/Athens.pdf>)
- » Holl, András and Makara, Gábor and Micsik, András and Kovács, László (2014) *MTMT: The Hungarian Scientific Bibliography*. In: Uses of open data within government for innovation and efficiency, 2014.06.30-2014.07.01, Samos. (<http://eprints.sztaki.hu/8020>)

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